

A MACHINE LEARNING PERSPECTIVE: FORECASTING CRIME TYPES AND INCIDENTS

¹Dr. R. Raja Kumar, Professor, Dept. of CSE

²Gundlapalle Vamsi, MCA Student, Department of Master of Computer applications,

^{1,2}Rajeev Gandhi Memorial College of Engineering and Technology, Nandyal, 518501, Andhra Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

In this era of recent times, crime has become an evident way of making people and society under trouble. An increasing crime factor leads to an imbalance in the constituency of a country. In order to analyze and have a response ahead this type of criminal activities, it is necessary to understand the crime patterns. This study imposes one such crime pattern analysis by using crime data obtained from Kaggle open source which in turn used for the prediction of most recently occurring crimes. The major aspect of this project is to estimate which type of crime contributes the most along with time period and location where it has happened. Some machine learning algorithms such as Naïve Bayes is implied in this work in order to classify among various crime patterns and the accuracy achieved was comparatively high when compared to pre composed works.

1. INTRODUCTION

Crime has become a major thread imposed which is considered to grow relatively high in intensity. An action stated is said to be a crime, when it violates the rule, against the government laws and it is highly offensive. The crime pattern analysis requires a study in the different aspects of criminology and also in indicating patterns. The Government has to spend a lot of time

and work to imply technology to govern some of these criminal activities. Hence, use of machine learning techniques and its records is required to predict the crime type and patterns. It imposes the uses of existing crime data and predicts the crime type and its occurrence bases on the location and time. Researchers undergone many studies that helps in analysing the crime patterns along with their relations in a specific location. Some of the hotspots analysed has become easier way of classifying the crime patterns. This leads to assist the officials to resolve them faster. This approach uses a dataset obtained from Kaggle open source based on various factors along with the time and space where it occurs over a certain period of time. We implied a classification algorithm that helps in locating the type of crime and hotspots of the criminal actions that takes place on the certain time and day. In this proposed one to impose a machine learning algorithms to find the matching criminal patterns along with the assist of its category with the given temporal and spatial data.

Crime prediction is a complex problem requiring advanced analytical tools to effectively address the gaps in existing detection mechanisms. With the increasing availability of crime data and through the advancement of existing technology,

researchers were provided with a unique opportunity to study and research crime detection using machine learning and deep learning methodologies. Based on the recent advances in this field [1][2][3], this article will explore current trends in machine learning and deep learning for crime prediction and discuss how these cutting-edge technologies are being used to detect criminal activities, predict crime patterns, and prevent crime. Our primary goal is to provide a comprehensive overview of recent advancements in this field and contribute to future research efforts. Machine learning is a subset of artificial intelligence that uses statistical models and algorithms to analyze and make predictions based on data. On the other hand, deep learning is a subset of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks with multiple layers to model complex relationships between inputs and outputs [4]. Both machine learning and deep learning technologies have the potential to be applied to the problem of crime prediction in many ways. Machine learning algorithms have been utilized in crime prediction to analyze crime data and predict future crime patterns. For example, algorithms like decision trees, random forests, and support vector machines have been trained on crime data from specific cities to predict crime patterns accurately [5]. Apart from predicting crime patterns, these algorithms can provide valuable insights into crime trends and patterns. These capabilities allow for deploying resources and tactics to combat crime effectively. Additionally, machine learning algorithms can also be used to identify correlations between crime incidents and

various environmental and demographic factors such as location, weather, and time of day [6]. This information can be used to develop crime prediction and prevention strategies suitable to a given community's specific needs. Predictive policing is also a significant application of machine learning for crime prediction [7]. Predictive policing refers to using data and analytics to inform law enforcement efforts and reduce crime. Machine learning algorithms can be used to analyze crime data from a specific geographic area, such as a city or neighborhood, to identify crime hotspots and predict future crime incidents. This information can then be used to direct policing resources to areas where they are most needed, increasing the effectiveness of law enforcement efforts. Deep learning algorithms, such as convolution and recurrent neural networks, have also shown promise in crime prediction. These algorithms have been trained on crime data with either a spatial or temporal component to accurately predict crime patterns in specific cities. For example, deep learning algorithms have been used to analyze crime data, including the time, location, and type of crime incidents [8]. This information is used to create a predictive model that can be used to identify potential crime hotspots and predict future crime incidents.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Crime Analysis Through Machine Learning

TO investigates machine-learning-based crime prediction. In this work, Vancouver crime data for the last 15 years is analyzed using two different data-processing

approaches. Machine-Learning predictive models, K-nearest-neighbour and boosted decision tree, are implemented and a crime prediction accuracy between 39% to 44% is obtained when predicting crime in Vancouver.

A Survey on Crime Occurrence Detection and prediction Techniques

Due to the increasing rate of crimes there is a need of system that will detect and predict crimes at dynamic time. The aim of this survey is to study Data Mining techniques that will help to detect and predict crimes using association rule mining, k-means clustering, decision trees & naive bayes and Machine learning techniques such as deep neural network and artificial neural network. Findings of this survey were that when the dataset instances have more number of missing values pre-processing becomes a vital task and crime does not occur uniformly across urban landscapes but concentrates in certain areas. So, predicting crime hotspots is a very important task also applying post-processing will help in lowering the rate of crimes.

SMART RESOURCE USAGE PREDICTION USING CLOUD COMPUTING FOR MASSIVE DATA PROCESSING SYSTEMS

Resource management plays the vital role in the cloud computing as the requirement for the massive data processing system such as health sectors, business solutions and the internet of things keeps on increasing in an exponential range. Allocation of proper and perfect resources remains as the main reasons for the successful computation of

the applications. However the conventional resources management methodologies, that totally depends on the simple heuristic based methods fails to accomplish a performance that is predictable. The appropriate resource allocation is directly related to the workload demand prediction as the would help to bring down the cost, time and power and the memory usage. The proposed method in the paper leverages the machine learning approaches to manage the resource allocation in the cloud computing for the massive data processing system, the simulation of the proposed model using the network simulator -2 enables to achieve a better performance and resources utilization at a decreased cost, time, power and memory usage.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

In pre-work, the dataset obtained from the open source are first pre-processed to remove the duplicated values and features. Decision tree has been used in the factor of finding crime patterns and also extracting the features from large amount of data is inclusive. It provides a primary structure for further classification process. The classified crime patterns are feature extracted using Deep Neural network. Based on the prediction, the performance is calculated for both trained and test values. The crime prediction helps in forecasting the future happening of any type of criminal activities and help the officials to resolve them at the earliest.

Disadvantages

1. The pre-existing works account for low accuracy since the classifier uses a

categorical values which produces a biased outcome for the nominal attributes with greater value.

2. The classification techniques does not suited for regions with inappropriate data and real valued attributes.

3. The value of the classifier must be tuned and hence there is a need of assigning an optimal value.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

❖ The data obtained is first pre-processed using machine learning technique filter and wrapper in order to remove irrelevant and repeated data values. It also reduces the dimensionality thus the data has been cleaned. The data is then further undergoes a splitting process. It is classified into test and trained data set. The model is trained by dataset both training and testing .It is then followed by mapping. The crime type, year, month, time, date, place are mapped to an integer for ensuring classification easier.

❖ The independent effect between the attributes are analysed initially by using Naïve Bayes. Bernouille Naïve Bayes is used for classifying the independent features extracted. The crime features are labelled that allows to analyse the occurrence of crime at a particular time and location. Finally, the crime which occur the most along with spatial and temporal information is gained. The performance of the prediction model is find out by calculating accuracy rate. The language used in designing the prediction model is python and

run on the Colab – an online compiler for data analysis and machine learning models.

Advantages

1. The proposed algorithm is well suited for the crime pattern detection since most of the featured attributes depends on the time and location.

2. It also overcomes the problem of analyzing independent effect of the attributes.

3. The initialization of optimal value is not required since it accounts for real valued, nominal value and also concern the region with insufficient information.

4. The accuracy has been relatively high when compared to other machine learning prediction model.

5. SYSTEM DESIGN

6. IMPLEMENTATION

MODULES DESCRIPTION

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and

password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Train and Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Predicted Crime Type Details, Find Crime Type Ratio on Data Sets, Download Trained Data Sets, View Crime Type Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user’s details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like POST CRIME DATA SETS, PREDICT CRIME TYPE, and VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

7. SCREEN SHOTS

INCIDENT_NUMBER	OFFENSE_CODE	OFFENSE_CODE	GROUP/OFFENSE	DESCRIPTION	DISTRICT	REPORTING_AREA	OCCURRED_ON_DATE	YEAR	MONTH	DAY
1182070945	808	Larceny	LARCENY ALL OTHERS		D14	808	2018-09-02 19:00:00	2018	9	
1182070943	1402	Vandalism	VANDALISM		C11	347	2018-08-21 00:00:00	2018	8	
1182070941	3440	Towed	TOWED MOTOR VEHICLE		D4	151	2018-09-03 19:27:00	2018	9	
1182070940	3114	Investigate Property	INVESTIGATE PROPERTY		D4	272	2018-09-03 21:16:00	2018	9	
1182070938	3114	Investigate Property	INVESTIGATE PROPERTY		B3	421	2018-09-03 21:05:00	2018	9	
1182070936	3820	Motor Vehicle Accident Response	MV ACCIDENT INVOLVING PEDESTRIAN - INJURY		C10	398	2018-09-03 21:09:00	2018	9	
1182070933	724	Auto Theft	AUTO THEFT		B2	330	2018-09-03 21:25:00	2018	9	

7. CONCLUSION

In this project the difficulty in dealing with the nominal distribution and real valued attributes is overcome by using two classifiers such as Multi nominal NB and Gaussian NB. Much training time is not required and serves to be the best suited for real time predictions. It also overcomes the problem of working with continuous target set of variables where the existing work refused to fit with. Thus the crime that occur the most could be predicted and spotted using Naïve Bayesian Classification. The performance of the algorithm is also calculated by using some standard metrics. The metrics include average precision, recall, F1 score and accuracy are mainly concerned in the algorithm evaluation. The accuracy value could be increased much better by implementing machine learning algorithms.

FUTURE SCOPE

In the future scope for forecasting crime types and incidents from a machine learning perspective is vast and holds promise for enhancing public safety, improving resource allocation, and addressing the underlying social determinants of crime. However, it also requires careful consideration of ethical,

legal, and societal implications to ensure that these technologies are deployed responsibly and equitably.

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